

at $\mu=0$ gave $\log K_1$ and the slope β_1 . The values of pK_1 thus found and those recalculated from Hamer, Pinching and Acree's data are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3— pK_1 OF REACTION, $H_2Ph \rightleftharpoons H^+ + HPh^-$

Temp. K	pK_1	
	Recalculated from H.-P.-A.	From cell (U-2)
283.15	2.930 ± 0.0007	2.930 ± 0.002
288.15	2.934 ± 0.0003	2.937 ± 0.0007
293.15	2.942 ± 0.0004	2.940 ± 0.002
298.15	2.956 ± 0.0025	2.955 ± 0.002
303.15	2.962 ± 0.0009	2.965 ± 0.002
308.15	2.967 ± 0.0021	2.967 ± 0.001
313.15	2.979 ± 0.0008	2.975 ± 0.002
318.15	2.986 ± 0.0004	2.987 ± 0.002
323.15	2.996 ± 0.0005	2.997 ± 0.002

It will be seen from Table 3, that the two sets of pK_1 values at all the temperatures closely agree with each other, and only at 313.15 K the difference goes upto 0.004.

The linearity of the plots and the agreement in pK_1 values shown in Table 3 indicate that modified Davies equation fairly correctly represents the activity coefficient of ions at least upto $\mu=0.1$ mol kg^{-1} . Close agreement among the pK_1 values recorded in Table 3 may be taken to indicate that pK_1 value of oxalic acid reported by Sinha *et al.*⁸ are fairly accurate.

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Kinetics of Oxygen Transfer from Triphenylarsine Oxide to Triphenylphosphine in Molten State Monitored by Infrared Spectroscopy

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TERTIARYPHOSPHINES/arsines as well as their chalcogenides are known to form vast number of coordination compounds with different metal ions¹⁻⁶. However, there is no attempt in studying atom transfer reactions between organophosphorus and organoarsenic compounds based on difference in bond strengths of $P=X$ and $As=X$ ($X=O, S, Se$). Since these types of ligands (as such or in complexed form) find great use in different catalytic processes, it may be useful to know how a tertiaryphosphine/arsine is undergoing change. In case there is oxidation of phosphine say, how will one monitor oxygen transfer to phosphorus kinetically? For example, the reaction of manganese(II) chloride with triphenylphosphine yields $Mn(Ph_3PO)_2Cl_2$ and not $Mn(PPh_3)_2Cl_2$, mechanism of the oxidation is not known. In order to understand such atom transfer reactions, the system consisting of triphenylphosphine and triphenyl arsine oxide has been arbitrarily selected. The reaction

has been studied under nitrogen atmosphere (PO group absorbs at 1180 while AsO group at 880 cm^{-1}). This work reports our initial results.

In order to know the concentration of PO group, the area method has been employed. The intensity height method is not normally useful in infrared spectroscopy because the bands are usually broad. For conducting the experiment, a known weight, say 75 mg of 1 : 1 mixture of Ph_3P and Ph_3AsO was added to each vessel of a set of six or seven glass vessels immersed in oil-bath at temperatures of 215, 225 and 235° under nitrogen atmosphere. At regular intervals of 0,10, . 50 min, a sample tube was taken out and the reaction contents cooled immediately to stop the reaction. The ir spectrum of each sample was recorded in KBr pellets with KSCN as the internal standard (sample amount : 15 mg ; KBr 160 mg and KSCN 8 mg). The ir spectra were recorded with a Spectromom-2000 instrument. The areas of PO groups as a function of time, temperature and mole ratio were corrected with respect to the unit area of CN group and converted into the molar concentration with the help of a calibration curve prepared from Ph_3PO .

The rate of second order reaction was calculated using the relation

$$k = \frac{1}{at} \left(\frac{x}{a-x} \right) \quad (1)$$

where, a refers to concentration of Ph_3P and x to the concentration of Ph_3PO formed during the reaction. The rate constant values are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE REACTION

Time (h) min	215° k (mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹)	225° k (mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹)	235° k (mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹)
0	0	0	0
10	42.4	8.3	4.9
20	28.3	4.7	0.46
30	21.0	7.4	2.4
40	11.9	5.9	4.0
50	—	5.1	5.3

$$a = 2.56 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol.}$$

The data in Table 1 are consistent with a second order rate kinetics. It may be seen from the Table that the values of k fall in magnitude on changing the temperature from 215 to 235°. It was observed that at a temperature higher than 235°, viz. 245°, there was greater inconsistency in the k values. Hence, it is inferred from this data that the transfer of oxygen takes place more efficiently in the vicinity of 215° for the reaction under consideration. The mechanism of oxygen transfer is proposed as

This study fairly demonstrates that ir spectroscopy is suitable for studying such atom transfer reactions.

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Debenzylation and Oxidative Cyclisation of Certain 2-S-Benzyl-1,5-diaryl-2,4-isodithiobiurets with Elemental Sulphur

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THIOCARBAMIDE has been used as a debenzylating agent in the debenzylation of 2-S-benzyl-1,5-diaryl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (1) earlier¹. The present paper describes the debenzylation and oxidative cyclisation of certain 2-S-benzyl-1,5-diaryl-2,4-isodithiobiurets using elemental sulphur.

2-S-Benzyl-1,5-diphenyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (1a) on reaction with elemental sulphur in presence of pyridine in boiling ethanolic medium afforded two products, one with m.p. 178° and the other with m.p. 203°. The ir spectrum of the product with m.p. 178° showed the presence of $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (1580), ν_{ringNH} (3350) and $\nu_{\text{S-S}}$ (500 cm⁻¹). The product was assigned the structure, 3,5-diphenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (2a) on the basis undepressed m.m.p. with the authentic sample². The product with m.p. 203° was found desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. Its ir spectrum showed the presence of ν_{NH} (3140) and $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ (1060 cm⁻¹). On the basis of these observations, it has been detected as 1-phenyl-3-(benzothiazole-2-yl)thiocarbamide (4a). This has been further confirmed by its comparison with an authentic sample³.

Neither benzylmercaptan nor dibenzyldisulphide could be isolated in the reaction. However, an odour of benzaldehyde was quite perceptible.

This reaction has been found to be capable of extension to other 2-S-benzyl-1,5-diaryl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (1b and 1c) and the corresponding 1,2,4-dithiazolidines (2b and 2c) and 1-phenyl-3-(chlorobenzothiazol-2-yl)thiocarbamides (4b and 4c) have been isolated (Table 1).

